

D1.2 Data Management Plan

30/09/2025

Abstract

This first Data Management Plan (DMP) introduces a report that specifies how research data will be collected, processed, monitored, and catalogued, following the FAIR principles. This deliverable is viewed as a living report that will advance throughout the life of the project.

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Table of content

Document Description	2
Revision History	2
Table of content	3
Tables	5
Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1. Purpose and scope of the document	7
1.2. Structure of the document	8
2. Data Summary	9
2.1. Origin of the project outputs reused or newly generated	9
2.2. Existing data/software and newly generated project outputs	10
2.3. Expected size of the data	11
2.4. Formats of the project outputs	11
3. FAIR Data	12
3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	12
3.1.1 Findability of data/research outputs	12
3.1.2 Metadata	12
3.1.3 Persistent identifiers	14
3.2. Making data accessible	14
3.2.1 Accessibility of data/research outputs	14
3.2.2 Repositories	15
3.2.3 Availability of the project outputs	15
3.2.4 Standardised access protocol	16
3.2.5 Metadata availability	16
3.3. Making data interoperable	16
3.3.1 Interoperability of data/research outputs	16
3.4. Increase data re-use	17
3.4.1 Reusability of data/research outputs	17
3.4.2 Examples of Research Outputs	18
4. Allocation of Resources	19
4.1. Data Management responsibilities	19
5. Data Security	20
6. Ethical Aspects	21
7. Data sets per WP	22
7.1. WP1 Project Coordination and Management	22
7.2. WP2 Innovation Management, Exploitation, Sustainability and Support	25
7.3. WP3 Data Commons Architecture	28
7.4. WP4 Analytics-Oriented Data Commons Discovery	31
7.5. WP5 Data Commons Preparation	34
7.6. WP6 Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment	37
7.7. WP7 Data Commons Use cases	39
8. Datasets per Use case	42

D1.2 Data Management Plan

8.1. cryo-EM SPA	43
8.2. DABAR	51
8.3. DaSCH	57
8.4. EODC	64
8.5. FAIR Molecular Dynamics	71
8.6. FinBIF	77
8.8. HAL	89
8.9. modama	95
8.10. NFDI4Earth	100
8.11. RRP	106
8.12. ScienceMesh and CERNBox	111
8.13. SWISSUbase	116
8.14. TopAnat	123
8.15. VIP	129
8.16. DANS - KNAW	134
9. Conclusions and next steps	140
9.1. DMP Change Management	140
Acronyms	141

Tables

Table 1 – Repository metadata	13
Table 2 – Document metadata	14

Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.2 – Data Management Plan – defines the structure within which EOSC Data Commons will create, manage, and collect data during the project's operations. Furthermore, it specifies how the data will be used or made available for verification and re-use, as well as how the data will be curated and stored once the project is completed.

In addition, the Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the FAIR design of the data, agreements on data security are created, and ethical issues associated with data collection/generation are addressed.

EOSC Data Commons adheres to [Horizon Europe Open Science FAIR principles](#) and strives to make data as open as possible, and as closed as necessary. The beneficiaries share the project's data in such a way that it is valuable to partners and their users outside the project, while ensuring that the privacy of third parties that participated in the data collection/generation is not violated.

Under these conditions, the data will be managed and released in compliance with the certifications and safeguards of the EU General Data Protection Regulation ([GDPR](#)). Every dataset is examined (in terms of sensitivity, privacy, and security) before an official decision is made on whether or not to make that specific information public.

1. Introduction

The current initial version of the DMP is composed of preliminary information and frameworks that will be followed. Hence, it is subject to updates in the future upon developments and changes during the project. In principle, the DMP describes the standards that will be used, how the project's research data will be stored and published for verification and reuse. EOSC Data Commons aims for full open access to data, following the FAIR principles.

1.1. Purpose and scope of the document

Open Science practices are implemented as an integral part of the proposed methodology and can be described as follows.

Firstly, the use case methodology involves open cooperative work for co-design based on the sharing of knowledge and relevant software solutions across scientific communities and IT experts. The cooperation with 12 national and institutional data repositories was initiated from M01. Consultations will be run online and open to all interested knowledge actors including open-source technology providers, major national and thematic data repositories, and user communities contributing to co-design, testing and validation with their use cases.

Secondly, co-design and validation are supported by making key exploitable results such as the software and the related documentation, the Interoperability Framework and requirements, open-source and open for exploitation under licenses listed as free by the Free Software Foundation and listed as "open-source" by the Open-Source Initiative. All project communication and dissemination outputs will be available under an open license (Creative Commons), allowing maximum uptake and reuse. Peer-reviewed scientific publications will be made open access in accordance with the European Commission Open Access policy for publications: they will be self-archived upon publication in Zenodo and, if possible, published in an appropriate open access journal or platform.

Finally, pluggable, harmonised FAIR assessment Infrastructure & Tools from Research Infrastructures (RIs), EOSC projects (e.g. OSTRails) and other initiatives will be evaluated for integration with the EOSC Data Commons services to offer researchers a toolset to increase the FAIRness of recently produced data (from instrumentation or as a result of analysis). EOSC Data Commons delivers technical capabilities that allow them to discover, access, share and use data from a federation of thematic, national and institutional repositories.

Although EOSC Data Commons will not manage all data assets directly, this document establishes a set of guidelines and best practices. All parties involved are expected to comply with their data management activities.

1.2. Structure of the document

This document comprises the following sections:

- [Section 1](#) presents an introduction to the project and the document.
- [Section 2](#) presents the purpose of data collection, type and format, origin of the data and its expected size.
- [Section 3](#) outlines EOSC Data Commons FAIR data strategies.
- [Section 4](#) briefly describes the allocation of resources.
- [Sections 5](#) and [6](#) outline data security and ethical aspects.
- [Section 7](#) shows the datasets per Work Package (WP).
- [Section 8](#) shows the datasets per Use Case.
- [Section 9](#) presents the conclusion and next steps.

2. Data Summary

In this chapter, we describe the various types of data the EOSC Data Commons consortium will handle during the project's lifetime. Some assets will be managed directly by the WPs, while others will be managed by scientific communities independently.

2.1. Origin of the project outputs reused or newly generated

The EOSC Data Commons work plan will mainly generate research outputs of the following types: data, software, and workflows, in addition to publications and documentation. Data will be stored in a way that adheres to the FAIR principles, ensuring findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

Data reused or newly generated within the project Work packages will be provided from primary sources (project members) and secondary sources (e.g. external websites, documents, expert feedback, surveys).

The use cases in EOSC Data Commons will help to shape the development of the project's core services: EOSC Matchmaker and EOSC Data Player. They can be grouped into four categories:

- Virtual Research Environments (VREs): codes will be written by developers in CERN, input data will be provided by the user of the services, output data are the results of computations by the services;
- Data Repositories: datasets as a result of computations performed on the national tier-1 HPC resource Supek, data stored in internal repositories (e.g. <https://hal.science/>), providers in the Earth System Sciences (e.g. re3data, Helmholtz Earth and Environment DataHub, ...), SWISSUbase;
- Data Repositories + VREs: data stored in internal repositories (e.g. DaSCH repository), Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, the Bgee database (www.bgee.org), [Girder warehouse](#) at CREATIS
- Workflows: data will be stored in public archives, e.g. the Protein Data Bank (PDB; e.g. <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/>) for experimental structures or the AlphaFold database (<https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/>) for computational models, the BioMagResBank (<https://bmr.io/>), EMPIAR (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar/>), scipion container recipes are placed at <https://github.com/I2PC/scipion-containers/> and TOSCA recipes can be found at <https://github.com/grycap/tosca>

2.2. Existing data/software and newly generated project outputs

The EOSC Data Commons project builds on both existing datasets and software as well as newly generated outputs, which are crucial to achieving the project's objectives.

Existing Data/Software

EOSC Beyond will leverage existing data and software components that are foundational to the project's work. These include:

- **Existing Data:** The data processing pipeline will create a Scipion (<https://scipion.i2pc.es/>) project and new outputs such as: CTFs, coordinates, particles and volumes. Apart from this, one of the use cases will use/create other kinds of data: container-related files and TOSCA files used for deployment orchestration. **DABAR** will re-use data from repositories hosted in DABAR, which might result in the generation of new data. The data will also be derived from internal repositories and databases, as well as data harvested from participating repositories, and from tool inventories such as Galaxy and WorkflowHub. EODC will re-use existing Earth observation datasets from the EODC data repository. This reuse will generate new data in the form of pre-processed, cloud-native data cubes optimised for time-series analysis. These new data products will be made discoverable and accessible through the EOSC Matchmaker. The project also generates data in RDF (Resource Description Framework) format, as a unifying format for all types of resources provided (e.g. educational resources, publications, datasets, standards, repositories, etc). Codes will be stored in GitHub repositories. Re-use of data acquired by VIP will be done on the PLoT imaging platform at CREATIS.
- **Existing Software:** The consortium members will use the following existing software solutions during the EOSC data Commons project implementation: SCIPION - Software Platform integrating multiple Software Packages into a graphical workflow; Code available under license type GPL v2+ and v3; Open-source code available under license type GPL4 and MIT license; Virtual Imaging Platform (VIP); REVA – Open Source software; SCIENCE MESH– Open Source software; interLink.; S-043-2020-OSCAR – Serverless Computing Platform for Data Processing Applications; Reproducible Research Platform (RRP).

Individual Data Management Plans (DMPs) are maintained by service owners for these existing datasets and software, ensuring they are used appropriately within the project's scope.

Newly Generated Project Outputs

The project will generate a wide range of new data and software outputs, which will be carefully managed and documented to ensure they adhere to FAIR principles. These outputs include:

Newly Generated Data:

- Research Data: This includes newly collected experimental data, survey results, and other forms of primary data specific to the research objectives of EOSC Data Commons.
- Knowledge Graph Data: Generated as part of the project's effort to interlink datasets and metadata, facilitating enhanced search and discovery functionalities within the EOSC ecosystem.
- Service-Specific Datasets: Data produced by specific services within the EOSC Data Commons project, which will be catalogued and stored following best practices in data management.

Newly Developed Software:

- Custom Tools: Software specifically developed during the project to address unique research needs, including enhanced versions of existing tools or entirely new applications.
- Workflows and Scripts: New workflows, including those for data processing, analysis, and visualization, particularly in Python and other relevant programming languages. These will be documented and shared through platforms like GitHub to ensure reusability.
- API Integrations, Connectors: APIs developed to enhance interoperability between datasets and services, conforming to international standards to facilitate integration within the broader EOSC infrastructure.

New Metadata:

The EOSC Data Commons project can produce enhanced metadata that ensures data and services compliance with the FAIR principles, which are essential for making data & services easy to find, access, and reuse across different research domains. All newly generated project outputs will be stored in open repositories, such as Zenodo and GitHub, under appropriate open licences (e.g., CC BY for data and permissive open-source licences for software). This ensures that the outputs are accessible, interoperable, and reusable by the broader research community.

2.3. Expected size of the data

The expected size of each dataset can be found in section [8 Datasets per WP](#) and section [9 Datasets per Use Case](#).

2.4. Formats of the project outputs

[Sections 8](#) and [9](#) show the estimated datasets that EOSC Data Commons is expected to produce and collect. This list is subject to modifications, including the addition or removal of datasets and their content in the later versions of DMP, depending on the project developments.

3. FAIR Data

In this section, we outline the EOSC Data Commons policies and best practices concerning FAIR publication of research data assets. EOSC Data Commons is committed to the publication of research data according to the FAIR principles. The applicable FAIR principles are described in what follows. (Communities: the list of communities can be found in section [9 Datasets per Use Case](#))

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Findability of data/research outputs

Output data, including detailed information for its generation (i.e. workflows), resulting from the project Use cases will be deposited and preserved following FAIR principles with the support of: (1) the federation of national and institutional repositories from the providers in the consortium, (2) the long-term access and preservation infrastructure of EOSC that will be implemented with the support of the call HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-04, and (3) Zenodo.

Data will only be restricted when required by regulatory or legal constraints or due to the owner's legitimate interests. Raw data from consultations (like user surveys and questionnaires) will be aggregated and anonymised to ensure it can be reused for future purposes. The software components from EOSC Data Commons will be published on publicly available git-based platforms. Matchmaker is a novel service of the project and will aid in the findability of datasets and tools.

3.1.2 Metadata

The metadata required by data repositories will be used, as outlined in Table 1. For documents, EOSC Data Commons has defined a standard set of metadata that should be used, as shown in table 2.

Element	Definition
Title	A name given to the source.
Upload type	e.g., dataset, workflow
Abstract	Describing the document contents and main conclusions.
Submitter	The person submitting the document to the repository
Authors	The people involved in writing significant portions of the

D1.2 Data Management Plan

Element	Definition
	document.
DOI	Provided by the resource
Publication date	The date of first publication.
Version	The version number generated by the document repository for the repository identifier. Versioning rule: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • +0.1 – new version of draft • +1.0 – new version of approved document
Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource.
Keywords	A list of words that will support the search within the repository service
Communities	A specific community in which the upload will appear.
License	Specifying the copyright status under which the upload will be licensed under.
Modify	The groups that are able to modify the document. The ‘office’ SSO group must be always marked.

[Table 1 – Repository metadata](#)

Element	Definition
Title	A name given to the source. For milestones and deliverables as described in the Description of Work.
Lead Partner	The recognised short name of the lead partner within the EOSC Data Commons project.
Authors	The people involved in writing significant portions of the document.
Reviewers	The people involved in reviewing the document.
Copyright status	The material is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License
Document type	e.g., deliverable, report, white paper
Status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft - the document is being prepared • Under EC review - the document is submitted to the EC portal and not approved yet by European Commission • Approved by EC - the document is approved by European Commission • Final - status of the document
Dissemination Level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public - can be shared without restrictions • Confidential - can be shared only with European Commission and project partners

Element	Definition
Document link	The URL in the document repository that provides access to the document on DocDB .
Digital Object Identifier	An identification number assigned through a repository service.
Keywords	A list of words that will support the search within the Zenodo service
Abstract	Describing the document contents and main conclusions.

[Table 2 - Document metadata](#)

3.1.3 Persistent identifiers

All research data assets produced within the project must be associated upon publication with a persistent and dereferenceable identifier. For public repositories, we will adopt the identifiers provided by the resource. For workflows, a DOI will be minted through GitHub. Outputs submitted to Zenodo will be assigned a DOI through this service. For code, we will adopt the practices of the developers community of the software we are building on.

Search keywords for discovery

Keywords will be created and then used to tag research output in Zenodo and in other registries or repositories (GitHub, OpenAIRE, EOSC catalogue, WorkflowHub, Software Heritage).

3.2. Making data accessible

3.2.1 Accessibility of data/research outputs

All research data assets produced within the EOSC Data Commons project must be published in such a way that they are accessible to others. As a general rule, EOSC Data Commons will consider as “accessible data” all research data assets exposed through one or more of the suitable, public community repositories.

Textual research outputs such as reports and presentations will be made available to the EOSC Data Commons Community on Zenodo upon release, under a permissive licence like CC BY 4.0. Sensitive legal, personal, or financial information will be restricted to authorised project partners, with access controls managed through secure platforms like the EGI Document Repository.

[cryo-EM SPA](#): Data published at EMDB and EMPIAR can be accessed without restrictions.

[DABAR](#): Data on DABAR is accessible through a free and standardised access protocol - HTTP. To access datasets with restricted access, eduGAIN authentication and affiliation to some institution are needed.

[DaSCH](#): Access to datasets on the DaSCH repository is determined by the data depositors. Many datasets are published under open access.

[EODC](#): Data access is supported via HTTP data server, S3 buckets, web interfaces (e.g., STAC Browser, PyGeoAPI), APIs (STAC API, OGC Features API), direct file download, FTP (for some datasets), and virtual machines. Workflows are going to be hosted in public repositories.

[ScienceMesh and CERNBox](#): All code will be publicly available.

[SWISSUbase](#), [DANS](#): Openly available datasets are published under Creative Commons licenses.

[TopAnat](#): All data is openly available under a public domain dedication CC0.

All data will be accessible via a standard URL or DOI, with metadata openly available to ensure comprehensive documentation and discoverability. Special consideration will be given to personal data, which will be anonymised before sharing, and proprietary data, which will be subject to access restrictions as per legal agreements.

3.2.2 Repositories

All documents, presentations and other materials that form an official output of the project (not just milestones and deliverables) are placed in the document [repository \(DocDB\)](#) to provide a managed central location for all materials. In addition, public deliverables and publications will be shared publicly via the [Zenodo platform](#) to increase the discoverability of the project outputs.

All profiles, specifications, configuration files, software, workflows, and code will be deposited in Zenodo and GitHub or according to the policy of the partner owning them. Therefore, the EOSC Data Commons will use DocDB, Zenodo, and GitHub as its standard and main repositories.

3.2.3 Availability of the project outputs

All deliverables, including documentation and guidelines necessary for (new) users after the project end as well as open source software will be available as project outputs well beyond the project lifespan. This will ensure continuous uptake, and the possibility of creating new modifications and add-ons will be available for new and existing users and contributors even after the project ends.

As for the services, they will be onboarded to the EOSC resource hub and any other relevant marketplace and therefore remain available. Updates and maintenance will be carried out by the EOSC Data Commons Open Source Community the project intends to set up and promote. In addition, the project will leverage the Horizon Results Platform to increase visibility and potential further exploitation of the results.

3.2.4 Standardised access protocol

All data will be accessible via URL or DOI. There will be no restrictions on the use of the research outputs, both during and after the end of this project. People accessing the data will not need to be identified and there is no need for a data access committee.

3.2.5 Metadata availability

Metadata containing information to enable users to access the data will be openly available under CC0 license and published together with the data, same repositories as listed under [3.2.2 Repositories](#). There is no time limit on metadata and data availability.

The EOSC Data Commons project acknowledges the value of documentation for interoperability purposes, increased uptake by different communities, and will encourage data owners to document their research data assets. EOSC Data Commons does not enforce specific provisions on documentation as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the mentioned repositories and properly curated according to the repository's best practices.

Research data itself should not be considered self-documenting and each published asset must be associated with sufficient documentation resources accessible through a public URL. Documentation must be browsable and include hypertext references to facilitate its fruition. Recommended documentation formats include markdown, HTML, and other markup languages. The inclusion of machine-readable documentation, such as OpenAPI, where applicable, is thoroughly encouraged. If a scientific publication is tied to the research data asset, the publication itself should be referenced and/or made available as part of the documentation.

3.3. Making data interoperable

3.3.1 Interoperability of data/research outputs

The EOSC Data Commons consortium acknowledges the importance of data interoperability: if a data asset cannot be compared, merged, or otherwise integrated with other assets, then its publication would bring little or no value to the community. The consortium is therefore committed to supporting and enforcing data interoperability.

cryo-EM SPA: Schemas defined by OSCEM will be used.

DABAR: Metadata are mapped to standard schema: Dublin Core, Metadata Object Description Schema, Data Cite.

DaSCH: Data curators ensure that all data available on the DaSCH repository is published in an open format and/or in a format that is widely recognized as a standard in the respective disciplines.

EODC: EODC follows community-endorsed standards such as STAC, OGC APIs (Features API, CSW, WCS), and RESTful metadata services. Data is accessible via interoperable

formats and protocols, including HTTP, S3, FTP, and tools like STAC Browser and PyGeoAPI, supporting cross-disciplinary data exchange and reuse.

FinBIF: For data formats, GeoPackages, CSV, (Geo)JSON and Excel formats will be used. FinBIF APIs follow the most recent standards (e.g. OGC API Features).

HADDOCK3 and DeepRank: The PDB format is a well-established standard for sharing coordinates of 3D structures.

HAL: Use of common standards for metadata: Dublin Core, DCterms, BibTeX, DataCite, TEI, OpenAIRE, Codemeta (for software), RDF.

NFDI4Earth: Several vocabularies, such as Schema.org and dcat, will be re-used. The best practices on spatial data provision on the Web (<https://www.w3.org/TR/sdw-bp/>) during publishing will be followed.

SWISSUbase: Data curators ensure that all data available on SWISSUbase is published in an open format and/or in a format that is widely recognised as a standard in the respective disciplines.

TopAnat: Bgee is recognised as an ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability resource (<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/interoperability/riis>). It re-uses several domain-specific ontologies and general-purpose vocabularies such as schema.org.

3.4. Increase data re-use

3.4.1 Reusability of data/research outputs

Reusability ensures that data and research outputs remain valuable beyond their initial use, enabling future studies, validation efforts, and broader scientific impact. By applying standardised licensing, enriching metadata, and archiving high-value datasets, research infrastructures are laying the groundwork for long-term accessibility and reuse. The following examples highlight how infrastructures are supporting reusability within the FAIR framework:

cryo-EM SPA: Scipion projects are designed to be reusable, so anyone can reproduce the analysis by having the JSON workflow file and the input data.

DABAR: All documentation, including README, should be included in the dataset by the depositors and repository managers.

DaSCH and SWISSUbase: All datasets on the DaSCH/SWISSUbase repository are published with rich metadata. Research specialists verify whether additional documentation or README files have been provided to include any necessary information.

EODC: The data will include references to other datasets where applicable. These references are provided through STAC metadata and supporting documentation in the Jupyter notebooks.

FinBIF: Readme files will be provided when users download data and some code examples will be published in GitHub.

TopAnat: Readme files, tutorial and documentation as markdown and rendered in the Bgee website.

3.4.2 Examples of Research Outputs

Software [S], Data [D], Workflows [W]

cryo-EM SPA: [W], [D] Workflows, containers, recipes and images and TOSCA files will be placed in a trusted repository so they can be re-used: workflows at WorkflowHub, container recipes at Github (<https://github.com/I2PC/scipion-containers/>), container images at rinchen.cnb.csic.es and TOSCA recipes at <https://github.com/grycap/tosca>.

DaSCH: [S] Any software produced as part of the project will be available as open source and published openly.

EODC: [S], [D], [W] Digital research outputs generated or re-used in the project, i.e. software components, automated workflows, and processing scripts, will be documented, versioned, and shared in public code repositories (e.g., GitHub), using open licences to promote reuse. Where possible, these digital outputs will also follow FAIR principles.

HADDOCK3 and DeepRank: [S] The software behind the WeNMR services is open and freely available on GitHub under [GitHub.com/haddock](https://github.com/haddock). The software of the webportal (wenmr.science.uu.nl) is also on GitHub, but as a private repository because of security issues, on <https://github.com/haddocking/csbportal> (WeNMR portal software, private).

DANS: [S] Code will be archived in Software Heritage and described using CodeMeta. Landscape review and specifications are published openly as a project deliverable.

4. Allocation of Resources

Any expenses associated with the collection/production of FAIR data during the EOSC Data Commons activities are included in the project budget. These expenditures will be required to cover a variety of data processing and data management operations, ranging from data collection and documentation to storage and preservation to distribution and re-utilization.

These operations are a component of the WP that processes the relevant data; hence, the needed effort will be part of the relevant WP.

The expenses of long-term data preservation are minimal, by using the EGI Online Storage and Google Drive platforms. Using Zenodo and GitHub (both free of charge) ensures that costs for long-term preservation of the data are manageable. When applicable, a more accurate cost estimate will be provided at a later stage of the project.

4.1. Data Management responsibilities

Within the EOSC Data Commons project, the following roles and responsibilities are associated with Data Management:

- **WP leaders** oversee the organization of the data processing and quality assurance that take place inside the Work Package they are leading.
- **Task Leaders/Use Case leaders** oversee the data compiled/produced throughout the operation of the task that they are responsible for. In addition to that, they also make sure that the data are properly prepared to be shared among the partners and made publicly available when applicable.
- **Data Processors** are consortium members who execute processing operations on the compiled/produced data.
- **Quality and Risk Manager** monitors and supports the WP leaders and Task Leaders/Use Case leaders in keeping the DMP confluence pages up to date. In addition, reports the changes and processes via milestones and deliverables as specified in the Grand Agreement.

5. Data Security

Any gathered data will be securely handled throughout the entire duration of the EOSC Data Commons project to protect it from loss and unauthorized access. Personal data is only accessible to those who are authorized to access it.

All partners/beneficiaries responsible for processing personal data have the responsibility to ensure that the data remains protected under all necessary security controls (including backup policies and integrity checks) and access controls (identification, authentication, authorization) within their infrastructure. In the unfortunate event of a personal data breach, the project partners will notify their competent national supervisory authorities without delay, as well as the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach. At the same time, they will document any personal data breaches and all related information. Regarding open data, for security and for long-term preservation, EOSC Data Commons relies on EGI Document Repository, Zenodo, and GitHub.

6. Ethical Aspects

This project includes multi- and interdisciplinary collaboration to improve and accelerate data lifecycle management supporting discovery, analysis, deposition, preservation, sharing, use and reuse of research data in a European data and compute continuum. This continuum builds on the capabilities of the EOSC EU Node, national and European infrastructures for data-intensive research and a community of federated repositories from national, institutional and thematic initiatives across several sciences.

The project will develop AI capabilities in compliance with the EU Act on Artificial Intelligence and future EC legislation in the area. Any processing of user activities by the AI-system will be included as necessary consent in the Terms of Use and Acceptable User Policies. Nevertheless, the development of the Ethics management plan will take place at the beginning of the project to specify the quality, risk and ethics processes to be followed within the project, with the support and guidance of an Ethics mentor, who will be appointed by the Consortium to advise the project participants on ethics issues identification and handling.

The following actions will be taken to ensure compliance with ethics requirements and proper monitoring of the ethics and data protection issues raised till the project ends:

- Develop the Ethics management plan (D1.1 Project handbook and Ethics management plan due M06 and Project handbook and Ethics management plan update due M36).
- Produce Ethics assessments on ethics issues monitoring and Horizon Europe compliance, as expected by the European Commission (D1.3 Ethics assessment no.1 due M18 and D1.6 Ethics assessment no.2 due M36).
- Ensure the project's compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation EU 2016/679.
- Follow the data protection management system.
- Review the plan for use cases from an ethical perspective.
- Develop ethics procedures for relevant use cases (if needed).
- Identify and appoint an Ethics mentor to support the work.

7. Data sets per WP

7.1. WP1 Project Coordination and Management

WP/Task	WP1
Contact	Hien Duc Bui (EGI Foundation)
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project Documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metrics ● Risks ● Procedures ● Plans ● Meetings agenda ● Meetings participation list ● Meeting minutes ● Presentations ● Deliverables ● Mailing list archive ● External Feedback (surveys, events, etc) ● Promotional material (flyers, posters, branding materials, etc.) ● Other communication & dissemination material (multimedia, video, etc)
Data description: Origin of data	All the data will be produced and provided by project members.
Data description: Scale of data	<1GB
Standards and metadata	plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html . Multimedia such as jpg/jpeg, gif, tiff, png or video formats
Data sharing: Target groups	All project members and the EC Project office. Communication activities; will be publicly available focusing on the target audiences of the project: including users, technology providers and infrastructure providers
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications in peer-reviewed journals, conferences & events aiming to engage stakeholders

<p>Data sharing: Approach to sharing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared within the consortium and European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentations: Public presentations are made public via indico portal or external conference pages ● Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website and Zenodo portal. ● Mailing list archive: only accessible by the mailing list members. ● Publications will be available via the project website and EOSC Data Commons community on Zenodo Repository. ● Promotional and other audio-visual material will be available via the project website. 2. Shared with the Project office and management boards to support work, as well as with the European Commission. <p>Unless otherwise stated all content will be available under the CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under the CC0 license. Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation</p>	<p>Once the project is finished, all the information will be preserved by the EGI Foundation for at least 5 years as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications will also be kept in the Zenodo Community.</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Duc Hien BUI</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p>Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal. Deliverables, publications and other dissemination material are shared via the Zenodo portal, which grants long-term preservation</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well</p>	<p>To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.</p>

D1.2 Data Management Plan

as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data Commons relies on EGI Document Repository, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms.
Other issues	
<i>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</i>	EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.

7.2. WP2 Innovation Management, Exploitation, Sustainability and Support

WP/Task	WP2
Contact	Xavier Salazar Forn (EGI Foundation)
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documents (e.g. meeting minutes, deliverables, publications, mailing list archive), • Slides (e.g. project presentations, training material), • Promotional material (e.g. printed such as flyers, posters, branding materials, etc, online - EOSC Data commons website, social media content, github, etc), audio-visual material (e.g. videos), • Database (Stakeholder - including when necessary names & contact data), • Feedback surveys
Data description: Origin of data	primary sources (project members) & secondary sources (external websites, documents, expert feedback, surveys etc)
Data description: Scale of data	< 1GB
Standards and metadata	plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html. Multimedia such as jpg/jpeg, gif, tiff, png, svg, mp4.
Data sharing: Target groups	T2.1: all project members and the EC Project office. T2.2 and T2.3: publicly available focusing on the target audiences of the project: including users from Scientific communities mainly and future industrial and public authority potential users.
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications on peer reviewed journals, on open research europe, scientific conferences, and pre-prints on relevant repositories if needed.

<p>Data sharing: Approach to sharing</p>	<p>Shared within the consortium and European Commission via</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentations: Public presentations are made public via Indico or external conference pages. ● Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website and Zenodo community. ● Mailing list archive: Only accessible to the mailing list members. ● Publications will be available via the project website and the EOSC Data Commons community on Zenodo Repository. ● Promotional and other audio-visual material will be available via the project website and on Zenodo where relevant. <p>Unless otherwise stated, all content will be available under a CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under a CC0 license following open science requirements in the grant agreement. Visual identity will follow the guidelines of the co-branding guidelines for INRFRAEOSC Projects and when possible shared under CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 license.</p> <p>Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space or e-mail</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation</p>	<p>Once the project is finished, all the WP2 information will be preserved by EGI Foundation for at least 5 years, as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications will be also kept on Zenodo Community</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Xavier Salazar Forn</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p>Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.</p>

D1.2 Data Management Plan

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data Commons relies on EGI Document Repository, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms.
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departamental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.

7.3.WP3 Data Commons Architecture

WP/Task	WP3
Contact	Enol Fernandez del Castillo (EGI Foundation)
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<p>Project Documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings agenda and minutes • Meetings participation list • Presentations • Deliverables • Mailing list archive • Publications, including technical specifications and architecture documentation <p>Documentation related to the service management of the EOSC Data Commons Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services, service endpoints, and service contacts • OLAs/UAs/SLAs for service delivery • Service logs generated by used WP3 services
Data description: Origin of data	All the data was produced and provided by project members. This includes members that use the services
Data description: Scale of data	< 1 TB
Standards and metadata	plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html. Confluence pages, Google docs; Multimedia such as jpg/jpeg, gif, tiff, png or video formats.
Data sharing: Target groups	<p>All project members and the EC Project office.</p> <p>Communication activities; will be publicly available focusing on the target audiences of the project: including users, technology providers and infrastructure providers</p>
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications on peer reviewed journals, conferences & events aiming to engage stakeholders

<p>Data sharing: Approach to sharing</p>	<p>Shared within the consortium and European Commission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentations: Public presentations are made public via Indico or external conference pages ● Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website. ● Mailing list archive: Only accessible to the mailing list members. ● Publications will be available via the project website and EOSC Data commons community on Zenodo Repository. Supporting material can be made available on GitHub EOSC Data Commons organisation. <p>Shared within the consortium:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Service management documentation: accessible to consortium members ● OLAs/UAs: accessible to consortium members and third parties supporting the service delivery <p>Unless otherwise stated all content will be available under the CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under the CC0 license. Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation</p>	<p>Once the project is finished, all the WP3 information will be preserved by the EGI Foundation for at least 5 years as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications will be also kept on Zenodo Community</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Enol Fernandez del Castillo</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p>Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal.</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	

D1.2 Data Management Plan

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data Commons relies on EGI Document Repository, GitHub, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms.
Other issues	
<i>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</i>	EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.

7.4.WP4 Analytics-Oriented Data Commons Discovery

WP/Task	WP4
Contact	Kurt Baumann / Tobias Schweizer / Sebastian Sigloch (SWITCH)
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project Documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metrics ● Risks ● Procedures ● Plans ● Meetings agenda ● Meetings participation list ● Meeting minutes ● Presentations ● Deliverables ● External Feedback (surveys, events, etc) ● Promotional material (flyers, posters, branding materials, etc.) ● Other communication & dissemination material (multimedia, video, etc) 2. Software documented on GitHub
Data description: Origin of data	All the data will be produced and provided by project members.
Data description: Scale of data	<1GB
Standards and metadata	plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html . Multimedia such as jpg/jpeg, gif, tiff, png or video formats
Data sharing: Target groups	All project members and the EC Project office. Communication activities; will be publicly available focusing on the target audiences of the project: including users, technology providers and infrastructure providers
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications in peer-reviewed journals, conferences & events aiming to engage stakeholders

<p>Data sharing: Approach to sharing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared within the consortium and European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentations: Public presentations are made public via indico portal or external conference pages ● Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website and Zenodo portal. ● Mailing list archive: only accessible by the mailing list members. ● Publications will be available via the project website and EOSC Data commons community on Zenodo Repository. ● Promotional and other audio-visual material will be available via the project website. 2. Shared with the Project office and management boards to support work, as well as with the European Commission. <p>Unless otherwise stated all content will be available under the CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under the CC0 license. Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation</p>	<p>Once the project is finished, all the information will be preserved by the EGI Foundation for at least 5 years as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications will also be kept in the Zenodo Community.</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Sebastian Sigloch</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p>Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal. Deliverables, publications and other dissemination material are shared via the Zenodo portal, which grants long-term preservation</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well</p>	<p>To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.</p>

D1.2 Data Management Plan

<p>as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data commons relies on EGI Document Repository, GitHub, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms</p>
<p>Other issues</p>	
<p><i>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</i></p>	<p>EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.</p>

7.5. WP5 Data Commons Preparation

WP/Task	WP5
Contact	Wim Hugo (DANS-KNAW)
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project Documentation <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Metrics b. Risks c. Procedures d. Plans e. Meetings agenda f. Meetings participation list g. Meeting minutes h. Presentations i. Deliverables j. Mailing list archive k. External Feedback (surveys, events, etc) l. Promotional material (flyers, posters, branding materials, etc.) m. Other communication & dissemination material (multimedia, video, etc) 2. Operational inventory data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Tools registry data b. Type registry data
Data description: Origin of data	All the data will be produced and provided by project members.
Data description: Scale of data	<1GB
Standards and metadata	plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html . Multimedia such as jpg/jpeg, gif, tiff, png or video formats
Data sharing: Target groups	All project members and the EC Project office. Communication activities; will be publicly available focusing on the target audiences of the project: including users, technology providers and infrastructure providers
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications in peer-reviewed journals, conferences & events aiming to engage stakeholders

Data sharing: Approach to sharing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared within the consortium and European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentations: Public presentations are made public via indico portal or external conference pages ● Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website and Zenodo portal. ● Mailing list archive: only accessible by the mailing list members. ● Publications will be available via the project website and EOSC Data commons community on Zenodo Repository. ● Promotional and other audio-visual material will be available via the project website. 2. Shared with the Project office and management boards to support work, as well as with the European Commission. <p>Unless otherwise stated all content will be available under the CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under the CC0 license. Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space</p>
Archiving and preservation	<p>Once the project is finished, all the information will be preserved by the EGI Foundation for at least 5 years as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications will also be kept in the Zenodo Community.</p>
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Wim Hugo
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal. Deliverables, publications and other dissemination material are shared via the Zenodo portal, which grants long-term preservation
Data Security	

<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>To manage the data generated by this WP, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.</p> <p>The data is openly available under a CC 4.0 BY licence for other users.</p> <p>Operational copies of the data will be deployed to the platform designated by EGI for use by the project.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data Commons relies on EGI Document Repository, GitHub, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms.</p>
<p>Other issues</p>	
<p><i>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</i></p>	<p>EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.</p>

7.6. WP6 Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment

WP/Task	WP6
Contact	Ales Krenek (CESNET)
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Project Documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meetings agenda Meetings participation list Meeting minutes Presentations Deliverables Publications Software
Data description: Origin of data	All the data will be produced and provided by project members.
Data description: Scale of data	<1GB
Standards and metadata	plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html; Confluence pages, Google docs; software repositories at https://github.com
Data sharing: Target groups	All project members and the EC Project office.
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications in peer-reviewed journals, conferences & events aiming to engage stakeholders
Data sharing: Approach to sharing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Shared within the consortium and European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentations: Public presentations are made public via indico portal or external conference pages Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website and Zenodo portal. Publications will be available via the project website and EOSC Data commons community on Zenodo Repository. Software will be made available at https://github.com/. <p>Unless otherwise stated all content will be available under the CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under the CC0 license. Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space</p>

Archiving and preservation	<p>Once the project is finished, all the information will be preserved by the EGI Foundation for at least 5 years as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications will also be kept in the Zenodo Community.</p> <p>Software will be maintained by WP partners on the best-effort basis.</p>
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Ales Krenek
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	<p>Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal. Deliverables, publications and other dissemination material are shared via the Zenodo portal, which grants long-term preservation. Software is expected to be taken over by the community, maintained as open-source as long as needed.</p>
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p>To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.</p>
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	<p>For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data commons relies on EGI Document Repository, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms</p>
Other issues	
<i>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</i>	<p>EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.</p>

7.7. WP7 Data Commons Use cases

WP/Task	WP7
Contact	Sebastian Luna Valero (EGI Foundation)
Data Summary	
Data description: Types of data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Project Documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metrics Risks Procedures Plans Meetings agenda Meetings participation list Meeting minutes Presentations Deliverables Mailing list archive External Feedback (surveys, events, etc) Promotional material (flyers, posters, branding materials, etc.) Other communication & dissemination material (multimedia, video, etc)
Data description: Origin of data	All the data will be produced and provided by project members.
Data description: Scale of data	<1GB
Standards and metadata	plain text such as .docx, .txt, .rtf, .pdf, .pptx, xml, .xls, .html . Multimedia such as jpg/jpeg, gif, tiff, png or video formats
Data sharing: Target groups	All project members and the EC Project office. Communication activities; will be publicly available focusing on the target audiences of the project: including users, technology providers and infrastructure providers
Data sharing: Scientific Impact	Scientific Publications in peer-reviewed journals, conferences & events aiming to engage stakeholders

<p>Data sharing: Approach to sharing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared within the consortium and European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentations: Public presentations are made public via indico portal or external conference pages ● Deliverables: All deliverables are shared within the consortium and also with the European Commission. Public deliverables are accessible to everyone via the project website and Zenodo portal. ● Mailing list archive: only accessible by the mailing list members. ● Publications will be available via the project website and EOSC Data commons community on Zenodo Repository. ● Promotional and other audio-visual material will be available via the project website. 2. Shared with the Project office and management boards to support work, as well as with the European Commission. <p>Unless otherwise stated all content will be available under the CC BY 4.0 license and metadata under the CC0 license. Any consortium-restricted content is shared via access-protected confluence space</p>
<p>Archiving and preservation</p>	<p>Once the project is finished, all the information will be preserved by the EGI Foundation for at least 5 years as well on the EC funding portal.</p> <p>Publications will also be kept in the Zenodo Community.</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Sebastian Luna Valero</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p>Long-term preservation is not needed, except from the contractual 5 years after the project. A copy of all the documentation of the project is kept by the European Commission in the funding portal. Deliverables, publications and other dissemination material are shared via the Zenodo portal, which grants long-term preservation</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well</p>	<p>To access the data shared only within the consortium, an EGI SSO account is required. Accounts and access management is the responsibility of the coordinator.</p>

D1.2 Data Management Plan

<p>as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>For security and long-term preservation, EOSC Data commons relies on EGI Document Repository, GitHub, Zenodo and Google Drive platforms</p>
<p>Other issues</p>	
<p><i>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</i></p>	<p>EGI Foundation will take care of the data according to the ISO 27000 standard for Information security management and GDPR.</p>

8. Datasets per Use case

The following listing describes the Data Management Plan for the Use Cases data that will be generated within EOSC Data Commons. For each dataset, it describes the type of data and its origin, the related metadata standards, the approach to sharing and target groups, and the approach to archival and preservation.

The Beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') in line with **the FAIR principles**. They should also ensure open access to research data via a trusted repository under the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. The requirements for research data management apply only to data that are generated in the course of the action. The Beneficiaries should also consider **re-used data** when developing their Data Management Plans (DMPs), if they form part of their research and to the extent possible.

- *Beneficiaries must establish a DMP, addressing important aspects of Research Data Management (RDM).*

The Beneficiaries should maintain the DMP as a living document and update it over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise. This includes, but is not limited to: the generation of new data, changes in data access provisions or curation policies, attainment of tasks (e.g. datasets deposited in a repository, etc.), changes in relevant practices (e.g. new innovation potential, the decision to file for a patent), changes in consortium composition.

The Beneficiaries are encouraged to encode their DMP deliverables as non-restricted, public deliverables, unless there are reasons (legitimate interests or other constraints) not to do so. In the case they are made public, it is also recommended that open access is provided under a CC BY licence to allow a broad re-use.

- *Beneficiaries must deposit the data in a trusted repository (see explanation above) and ensure open access through the repository, as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP.*

Deposition of data must take place as soon as possible after data production/generation or after adequate processing and quality control have taken place, providing value and context to the data and at the latest by the end of the project. This does not entail that data must be made open, but rather that it is deposited so that metadata information is available and hence information about the data is findable. In exceptional cases in which specific constraints apply (e.g. security rules), deposition can be delayed beyond the end of the project. Data includes raw data, to the extent technically feasible, but especially if it is crucial to enable reanalysis, reproducibility and/or data reuse.

The EOSC Data Commons project involves 16 multidisciplinary and thematic science repositories as well as scientific disciplines of Use cases.

8.1. cryo-EM SPA

WP/Task	WP7 - Task 7.2
Contact	Carlos Óscar Sorzano, Irene Sánchez López - The National Centre for Biotechnology (CNB-CSIS)
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<p><i>State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</i></p> <p>One of the goals of this use case is to allow CryoEM facilities to process the data acquired at their microscopes. Before testing this with new data, existing public data will be used. This raw data, consisting of movies or micrographs (movies aligned), will be taken from the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR) (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar/).</p> <p>Also, some of the workflows used for this data processing pipeline can be placed at WorkflowHub, more precisely in the "CryoEM facility workflows" collection: https://workflowhub.eu/collections/31</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	<p>The workflow will start from movies or micrographs and the data processing pipeline will create a Scipion (https://scipion.i2pc.es/) project and new outputs such as: CTFs, coordinates, particles and volumes.</p> <p>Apart from this, this use case will use/create other kinds of data: container-related files and TOSCA files used for deployment orchestration.</p>
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>Data will consist mainly of movies, micrographs, CTFs, coordinates, particles, 2d classes, volumes, 3d classes and data processing pipelines. The formats are basically .tiff, .psd, .xmd, .png, .txt, .stk, .pos, .mrc, .mrcs, .vol, .star, .json, .sqlite</p> <p>The container-related files formats are .def and .sif and the TOSCA files .yaml</p>

<p>What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>	<p>The purpose of re-using existing public data is to test the workflow pipeline and check if we can achieve good results. The purpose of generating new data is to use the workflow for processing movies recently acquired at CryoEM facilities.</p> <p>The goal of using container images is to set up the software in the machine and the TOSCA recipes to deploy these machines in the cloud.</p>
<p>What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?</p>	<p>CryoEM data size is quite big. Movies for one acquisition can easily reach 2/3 TiB and micrographs 1 TiB. The size of the rest of the Scipion project altogether with the remaining outputs would seize less than 1 TiB.</p> <p>Container image size is less than 50 GiB and TOSCA files are small, of few megabytes.</p>
<p>What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?</p>	<p>Re-used data will come from EMPIAR (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar/) New raw data would come from CryoEM facilities.</p> <p>Scipion container recipes are placed at https://github.com/I2PC/scipion-containers/ and the images are available at rinchen.cnb.csic.es (and can be downloaded with the aptainer command "aptainer pull oras://rinchen.cnb.csic.es/scipion/\$container-name").</p> <p>TOSCA recipes can be found at https://github.com/grycap/tosca</p>
<p>To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p>	<p>To the whole structural biology community, CryoEM facilities, research institutes, pharmaceutical companies, etc.</p>
<p>FAIR Data</p>	
<p>1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Re-used data yes, because we will use movies or micrographs from an EMPIAR entry. Let's say we use the micrographs of EMPIAR-10891, this entry has the DOI https://doi.org/10.6019/EMPIAR-10891</p> <p>The workflows used for the analysis can have a persistent identifier if one is deposited at WorkflowHub. For example, this one https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1755 can be always referred as https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1755?version=1</p> <p>New raw data won't have a persistent identifier unless the data analysis ends in a good volume and the authors want to publish it at the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) and submit the raw data to EMPIAR.</p>

	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>In the CryoEM field there is a recently created initiative called Open Science Community for Electron Microscopy (OSCEM), whose main goal is to create a standard that covers the full data lifecycle from data collection through publication. Several data schemas are now being defined (https://github.com/osc-em/OSCEM_Schemas) for describing the samples, instruments, acquisitions, data processing, etc. We aim to use this standard for describing the CryoEM data we will work with.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Don't think so.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Will be JSON/YAML files, so yes.</p>
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>As it is said before, if the authors achieve a good volume, at some point it will be published at EMDB and the raw data at EMPIAR. Both of them are the standard repositories used to deposit Electron Microscopy data, so yes, they are trusted repositories.</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>There is no need to create arrangements with the repositories, this is the standard procedure in Electron Microscopy.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes, both EMDB and EMPIAR. For example EMDB-13916 whose micrographs related to EMPIAR-10891 can always be related as https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/EMD-13916 and https://doi.org/10.6019/EMPIAR-10891 respectively.</p>

b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>It depends if the data processing pipeline ends in a good result or not. If the volume obtained is good enough, it will be eventually published at EMDB and if the data acquisition was funded with public money, in some research infrastructures such as Instruct-ERIC there are policies that enforce the authors to also publish the related raw data at EMPIAR. However, if the data processing outcome is unsatisfactory, the data may not be published anywhere.</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>It depends on the CryoEM facility. As it was said before and for the case of Instruct-ERIC, if the data acquisition was funded with public resources there is an embargo period of 3 years. After that, the raw data should be publicly available, either at EMPIAR if there is a publication or in a private repository in other cases.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>If the data is published at EMDB and EMPIAR, yes. EMDB volumes are relatively small and can be downloaded with HTTPS protocol and EMPIAR micrographs can be downloaded using HTTPS, FTP and GridFTP (Globus).</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Data published at EMDB and EMPIAR can be accessed without restrictions.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>There is no login system at EMDB or EMPIAR and there is no need for having it, so people won't be identified.</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No</p>

<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes, the metadata for EMDB entries are openly available at https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/api/entry/EMD-XXXXX (where XXXX is the entry id). For EMPIAR is the same, it can be retrieved from https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar/api/entry/XXXXX</p> <p>This metadata contains references to the DOI or the entry id, so yes, it will enable the user to access it.</p> <hr/> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>EMDB and EMPIAR are owned by the EMBL-EBI, a well established research organization funded by several member and associate states. So it's difficult for them to lose the funding for maintaining these repositories, so the data will be available and findable hopefully forever.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Yes, the EMDB entry describes which software has been used for the data processing (such as Scipion, Relion, Cryosparc, etc.).</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>We will use the schemas defined by OSCEM.</p> <hr/> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>No, each data processing pipeline will start from scratch with movies/micrographs and won't use any other existing data.</p>

<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Scipion projects are designed to be reusable, so anyone can reproduce the analysis having the JSON workflow file and the input data.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>If a publication is achieved, for sure volumes will be openly available at EMDB under CC0 license and if the facility belongs to a research infrastructure where it is mandatory for acquisitions publicly funded, the raw data will be placed at EMPIAR under CC0 too.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Could be. The resolved 3D structures could be used for any biological study afterwards.</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Yes, using OSCEM schemas.</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>The authors normally use validation software to check if the results are satisfactory. Also, EMDB has its own methods to check if the data submitted is good enough.</p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
<p>Other research outputs</p>	

<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Yes, apart from the CryoEM data there will be workflows, containers, recipes and images and TOSCA files, as they were described before. All of them will be placed in a trusted repository so they can be re-used: workflows at WorkflowHub, container recipes at Github (https://github.com/I2PC/scipion-containers/), container images at rinchen.cnb.csic.es and TOSCA recipes at https://github.com/grycap/tosca</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Carlos Óscar Sorzano and Irene Sánchez López</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Research outputs (workflows, container recipes and TOSCA recipes) are in public repositories so as long as WorkflowHub and Github projects are alive, they will be available.</p> <p>For the data published at EMDB and EMPIAR and it was said before, the previous statement applies here, depending on EMBL-EBI.</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>New movies or micrographs from upcoming acquisitions will be transferred from the CryoEM facility to the cloud machine where will be processed with Scipion using a secure method or protocol such as rsync or GridFTP.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>For the data published, we imagine EMDB and EMPIAR have data security policies implemented.</p>
<p>Ethical Aspects</p>	
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>Apart from the embargo period, no.</p>

D1.2 Data Management Plan

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	N/A
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<p><i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i></p> <p>The data could be acquired at a CryoEM Instruct-ERIC facility. In that case it should follow its data management procedures.</p>

8.2. DABAR

WP/Task	WP4, WP7
Contact	Draženko Celjak , Emir Imamagić - University of Zagreb (SRCE)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<i>Existing data from repositories hosted in DABAR will be used for purpose of EOSC Data Commons project within the work packages Analytics-Oriented Data Commons Discovery (WP4) and Data Commons Use cases (WP7)</i>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	We will re-use data from repositories hosted in DABAR which might result in generation of new data.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	The project will re-use metadata encoded by Dublin Core, DataCite and Metadata Object Description Schema.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Data repositories contain data generated by demanding computational algorithms on large-scale HPC systems. The purpose is to enable researchers to use the data without needing to do re-computation by themselves. DABAR (meta)data will be integrated with the EOSC Matchmaker to enhance discovery and reuse at the European level. Additionally, the data will be used for testing purposes.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	As of July 2025, the repositories included in the DABAR repository system contain 290 published datasets with a total size of 40 TB. DABAR will provide sufficient space for new datasets as we identify them later in the project.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	DABAR is a national repository system containing institutional and thematic repositories. Some of the current datasets are the result of computations performed on the national tier-1 HPC resource Supek. We expect more datasets to result from the work of researchers on this resource.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Data will be useful to anyone working in the area of computational chemistry and other scientific areas that will be covered by this use case.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Yes, DABAR assigns URN:NBN to each dataset.</p>
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes. Metadata can be harvested via OAI-PMH.</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>yes</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>yes</p>

<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Each dataset (and other types of digital object stored in DABAR) have access permission defined by the dataset depositors. Most of the dataset are openly available, but some datasets are published under restricted access, requiring users to authenticate via a federated login and affiliation with some specific institution. A smaller number of datasets are in closed access.</p> <p>Openly available datasets are published under Creative Commons licenses.</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>An embargo option is available when publishing datasets on the DABAR repository system, with the duration set by the data depositors.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Data on DABAR is accessible through a free and standardised access protocol - HTTP. To access datasets with restricted access eduGAIN authentication and affiliation to some institution is needed.</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Compliance with the access conditions set by data depositors will be ensured throughout the EOSC Data Commons project.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>Federated login via eduGAIN.</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No.</p>

<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes, all metadata exposed by DABAR are available under CC0.</p> <hr/> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Metadata will be retained indefinitely.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>If specific code or software is required, the data depositor will have provided relevant information in the documentation or metadata, or included the script directly with the dataset.</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Metadata are mapped to standard schema: Dublin Core, Metadata Object Description Schema, Data Cite.</p> <hr/> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>All documentation, including README, should be included in the dataset by the depositors and repository managers.</p>

	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>The decision to make data openly accessible or restricted is left to the data depositor. When open publication is possible, the depositor can choose from any of the Creative Commons licenses.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	TBD.
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i>
Data Security	

<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>All data is hosted on the infrastructure operated by SRCE. Physical access, backups, redundancy, authentication and other aspects are defined with SRCE rulebooks.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>Yes.</p>
<p>Ethical Aspects</p>	
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>No.</p>
<p>Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>	<p>n/a</p>
<p>Other issues</p>	
<p>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</p>	<p>No.</p>

8.3. DaSCH

WP/Task	WP7
Contact	Ivan Subotic - Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Existing data from the DaSCH repository will be utilized based on the specific needs and requirements of the EOSC Data Commons project. Most importantly, the available (meta)data will be integrated with the EOSC Matchmaker.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	The reuse of existing data from the DaSCH repository will not involve the generation of new data.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Data reuse will primarily focus on datasets from the humanities. Data will mostly be available in text form as well as audio, video, and image files. The specific file formats are predominantly open or widely recognized as standard within the respective disciplines.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	DaSCH metadata will be integrated with the EOSC Matchmaker to enhance discovery and reuse/analysis at the European level. Additionally, the data will be used for testing purposes.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The selection of data will be determined by the needs of the EOSC Data Commons project. Dataset sizes vary significantly depending on the types of data they contain. Technically, individual files can be as large as a few GB, with no upper limit on the overall size of a dataset. As of July 2025, the DaSCH repository hosts around 60 published datasets.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	All data has been published on the DaSCH repository.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Any researcher working with humanities data.
FAIR Data	

<p>1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Yes, each dataset in the DaSCH repository has an assigned ARK identifier.</p>
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>We have our own internal metadata schema. There is no standard metadata schema in the humanities. As part of this project, it is planned to implement export of the metadata in a standardized schema, which will also be determined during this project.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes, "keywords" is a mandatory metadata field for datasets published on the DaSCH repository.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Currently the metadata can be accessed through an API. As part of this project it is planned to implement access through OAI-PMH following a yet to be determined metadata standard.</p>
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>All data is available on the DaSCH repository.</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>The data has already been deposited, and since DaSCH is a use case partner in the EOSC Data Commons project, no arrangements are necessary.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>All datasets deposited in the DaSCH repository are assigned an ARK identifier.</p>

<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Access to datasets on the DaSCH repository is determined by the data depositors. Many datasets are published under open access. Some are published with restricted access, requiring users to authenticate via a federated login and obtain approval from the data depositor.</p> <hr/> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>No embargoed data will be used as part of this project.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Data on the DaSCH repository is accessible through a free and standardized access protocol. Users can download open access datasets without restrictions, while access to restricted datasets requires a login. Users can also retrieve specific datasets and files programmatically via an API.</p> <hr/> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Compliance with the access conditions set by data depositors will be ensured throughout the EOSC Data Commons project.</p> <hr/> <p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>No user identification is required for open access datasets. Access to restricted datasets requires a login.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No.</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes and metadata will contain information to enable the user to access the data.</p>

	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>All metadata remains available indefinitely. If a dataset is deleted, a tombstone page containing the metadata will be retained.</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>If specific code or software is required, the data depositor will have provided relevant information in the documentation or metadata, or included the script directly with the dataset.</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Data curators ensure that all data available on the DaSCH repository is published in an open format and/or in a format that is widely recognized as a standard in the respective disciplines. The metadata schemas adhere to discipline-specific standards, and a metadata user guide is available. Metadata is entered either through drop-down lists using controlled vocabularies or through free-text fields that follow specific input rules.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Within the project, the goal will more likely be to move towards a common standard rather than diverge from it, so this should not apply.</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Publications on the DaSCH repository follow the structure: project → dataset(s) → file(s), where each project can contain multiple datasets that are grouped together. Therefore, related datasets are referenced through their overarching project.</p>

<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Our research data specialists ensure that all datasets on the DaSCH repository are published with rich metadata. They also verify whether additional documentation or README files have been provided to include any necessary information. If such documentation is missing, the curators request the data depositor to add the required information or supplementary documents before the dataset is published.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>The decision to make data openly accessible or restricted is left to the data depositor. When open publication is possible, the depositor can choose from any of the Creative Commons licenses. Any data or software produced as part of this project will be made openly available in the public domain.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Any data or software produced as part of this project will be made openly available in the public domain, and can therefore be reused after the end of the project.</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Data depositors include provenance information within the metadata/documentation associated with their datasets. Details about authors and participating institutions are collected in the project-level metadata. Any data or software produced as part of this project will be thoroughly documented.</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>The metadata of every submitted dataset is thoroughly reviewed, and the data itself is spot-checked, by the curators at DaSCH. Each project and its associated datasets are assigned a curator. Any necessary corrections or additions are made in close consultation with the data depositor.</p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>

Other research outputs	
In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?	Any software produced as part of the project will be available as open source and published openly.
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Presumably, each use case partner will handle this individually.
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	All data in the DaSCH repository is retained for a minimum of 10 years.
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	All data of the DaSCH repository is hosted at the IT Services of the University of Basel with regular backups.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, the DaSCH repository.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in	The DaSCH repository does not take personal or sensitive data.

D1.2 Data Management Plan

questionnaires dealing with personal data?	
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	This is not anticipated.

8.4. EODC

WP/Task	WP7 - T7.2
Contact	Charis Chatzikyriakou - Earth Observation Data Centre (EODC)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Yes, we will re-use existing Earth observation datasets already hosted in the EODC data repository, including recent cloud-optimised datasets and older, non-optimised legacy data from previous years. These datasets will be re-used to demonstrate and validate our automated workflows, which will transform them into analysis-ready, cloud-native data cubes.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Yes, we will re-use existing Earth observation datasets from the EODC data repository. This reuse will generate new data in the form of pre-processed, cloud-native data cubes optimised for time-series analysis. These new data products will be made discoverable and accessible through the EOSC Matchmaker.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	The use case will re-use and generate Earth observation time-series data, primarily optical (e.g., Sentinel-2) and radar (e.g., Sentinel-1) datasets. The new data products will be cloud-native, analysis-ready data cubes stored in open, scalable formats such as Zarr, optimised for parallel processing with tools like xarray and Dask.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	To develop and demonstrate automated workflows that will simplify the data management for EO scientists. By transforming existing EO datasets into cloud-native, analysis-ready data cubes, the use case aims to enable efficient time-series analyses directly in the cloud.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The expected size of re-usable data is about 50 GB/day. The generated data are workflows and tools not expected to be exceeding 1 GB.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The data is sourced from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem. The derived data and tools will be made freely available via GitHub or in a similar open-source fashion.

<p>To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p>	<p>To Austrian, but not only, users who need easy and standardised access to satellite data products integrated with other geo-information. More broadly, it will benefit researchers and practitioners in Earth and Environmental Sciences, especially in fields like remote sensing, climate monitoring, biodiversity, hydrology, agriculture, and disaster risk management.</p>
<p>FAIR Data</p>	
<p>1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Partially, most re-used and generated data are currently not foreseen to be identified by a persistent identifier.</p>
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Yes, rich metadata will be provided to ensure that all data are easily discoverable and interoperable. Metadata will be created following the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification, which is widely adopted in the Earth observation community. This metadata will include details such as spatial and temporal extent, sensor type, acquisition date, processing level and others. By using STAC, the data will be machine-readable and compatible with discovery services like the EOSC Matchmaker, making it easier for users to search, access, and reuse the data products through standard interfaces and tools.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes, keywords and user-friendly interfaces for discovery are provided.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes, metadata will be provided in a machine-readable, STAC-compliant format, enabling it to be easily harvested and indexed by external catalogues and discovery services.</p>
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Yes, all re-used and newly generated data products will be deposited in the EODC data repository, which is a trusted, domain-specific repository that ensures secure, reliable, and standards-compliant long-term storage and access to Earth observation data.</p>

	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Yes. The EODC data repository is operated by our organisation and integrated into our infrastructure. This ensures that both the original datasets and the newly generated, cloud-native data cubes can be deposited, managed, and made accessible in line with project needs and FAIR data principles.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes, each item is assigned a unique identifier via STAC metadata which resolves to the corresponding digital objects (e.g., data files).</p>
<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Most data will be made freely available. For some datasets, a registration with an additional approval step is necessary. This depends on the license and access rights as established by the respective data providers.</p> <p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>Usually not applicable. If such a requirement comes up, this will be decided on a per case basis.</p> <p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Data access is supported via HTTP data server, S3 buckets, web interfaces (e.g., STAC Browser, PyGeoAPI), APIs (STAC API, OGC Features API), direct file download, FTP (for some datasets), and virtual machines. Workflows are going to be hosted in public repositories.</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>If restrictions apply, access to the data will be provided upon request and subject to approval during the project. After the project ends, access will continue under the same conditions, in accordance with the data providers' licensing and access policies.</p>

	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>Users accessing open data will not be identified, however, anonymized data usage access statistics based on IP addresses and characteristics (e.g., geolocation) might be derived. Users accessing restricted data will need to register an account and provide their name and email address.</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No, access to personal or sensitive data is not covered.</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes, metadata will be made openly available through both the STAC catalog and GitHub repository. While not all metadata is CC0 by default, selected collections will be explicitly licensed under CC0 where appropriate. The GitHub workflows are intended to be released under CC0 or a similarly permissive license. All metadata will include sufficient information to enable users to access the corresponding data.</p> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>The data will remain available and findable for as long as the hosting infrastructure allows, with efforts made to provide long-term accessibility. Even if the data itself becomes unavailable, the metadata will remain accessible to support discovery.</p> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Yes, documentation and references for any software needed to access, read, or process the data will be included. Where possible, the relevant software—especially workflows and tools—will be provided as open-source code via GitHub.</p>

<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>To ensure interoperability and reusability, EODC follows community-endorsed standards such as STAC, OGC APIs (Features API, CSW, WCS), and RESTful metadata services. Data is accessible via interoperable formats and protocols including HTTP, S3, FTP, and tools like STAC Browser and PyGeoAPI, supporting cross-disciplinary data exchange and reuse.</p>
	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Yes, if project-specific or uncommon ontologies or vocabularies are used, mappings to widely adopted standards will be provided. Any generated vocabularies will be openly published to support reuse, refinement, and extension by the community.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes, the data will include references to other datasets where applicable. These references are provided through STAC metadata and supporting documentation in the Jupyter notebooks.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Documentation will be provided via a GitHub repository including README files, Jupyter Notebooks, and STAC metadata.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>Data accessible via STAC will reflect the original sources and their respective licenses—ranging from open to restricted—while workflows, analyses, and derived products shared via GitHub will be openly licensed.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p>

	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Provenance will be documented via STAC metadata for source data, and added to GitHub workflows where applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Data quality assurance includes integrity checks at the file system level, and validation through STAC metadata before publication.</p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p> <p>Research outputs beyond data—such as workflows and tools—will be openly shared via GitHub.</p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Yes, in addition to data, we are also planning to manage other digital research outputs generated or re-used in the project, i.e. software components, automated workflows, and processing scripts. These outputs will be documented, versioned, and shared in public code repositories (e.g., GitHub), using open licences to promote reuse. Where possible, these digital outputs will also follow FAIR principles.</p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Charis Chatzikyriakou, Stefan Reimond</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Long-term preservation of workflows and tools on GitHub is expected due to platform stability, while STAC-linked data may vary in availability.</p>
Data Security	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving)</p>	<p>Secure multi-tier storage, firewalls, backup systems, and standard transfer protocols allow safe archiving, recovery, and handling of data.</p>

and transfer of sensitive data)?	
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, all data—both re-used and newly generated—will be safely stored in the trusted EODC data repository.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i> No.
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	N/A
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial /departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i>

8.5. FAIR Molecular Dynamics

WP/Task	WP7 - Task 7.2
Contact	Antonio Rosato - The Consorzio Interuniversitario Risonanze Magnetiche di Metallo Proteine (CIRMMP)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<p>Yes. Molecular dynamics simulations use as input a 3D structural model of the macromolecular system of interest (proteins; nucleic acids; combinations thereof). These are obtained experimentally or often retrieved from public archives: the Protein Data Bank (PDB; e.g. https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/) for experimental structures or the AlphaFold database (https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/) for computational models.</p> <p>Experimental data for verification of the simulation outcomes can also be taken from archives, such as the BioMagResBank (https://bmr.io/).</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Yes. Molecular dynamics simulations produce time-dependent trajectories that are now suitable for storage into databases for re-analysis also by independent researchers. Part of the aims of this task is to improve the protocols for trajectory deposition.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	3D structures in mmCIF or PDB format (text files), as well as various other input data (all as ASCII text files). Trajectories consist of bundles of 3D structures generated as a function of simulation time.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Obtain scientific insight into the motions of macromolecules and their adducts, which are relevant to numerous functional properties, from partner recognition to binding and transport of metabolites.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	<p>Input data: few MBs</p> <p>Output data: 100 MBs to 10 GBs</p>
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	<p>Input data are provided by the user of the services, also via the appropriate identifiers in the public archives mentioned above.</p> <p>Output data are the results of computations by the services.</p>

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	The data can be of interest to the biophysical and computational biology communities.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>This will depend upon the policies of repositories where the output data will be uploaded.</p>
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Various metadata recommendations for MD have been proposed in the literature, which will be reviewed in this task.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Work in progress.</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Work in progress.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>

b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>This will depend upon the user's requirements.</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>If made public, the data will be freely accessible</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No.</p>
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Work in progress</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>No. Yes.</p>

3.) Making data interoperable	<i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i>
	N.A.
	<i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i>
	N.A.
	<i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i>
	N.A.
4.) Increase data re-use	<i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i>
	These are provided by software developers
	<i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i>
	N.A. The data belong to users
	<i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i>
	N.A. The data belong to users
	<i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i>
N.A.	
	<i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i>
	N.A.
	<i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i>
Other research outputs	

<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>We will provide our own software via github as much as possible, taking into account any security concerns that might arise.</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>N.A. The data belong to users</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>Output data from simulations may be uploaded by the users to repositories.</p>
<p>Ethical Aspects</p>	
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p>
<p>Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>	<p>No</p>

Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	N.A.

8.6. FinBIF

WP/Task	WP7
Contact	Alpo Turunen (University of Helsinki)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	We will use existing data from laji.fi to make FAIR assessments and to connect our (meta)data to EOSC Matchmaker.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	The amount of data in laji.fi is increasing all the time but this project doesn't generate more data per se.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	This format will re-use existing species observations data from laji.fi. It can be used in many formats, such as tabular (CSV, TSV, Excel) or GIS formats (GeoPackage, GeoJSON). Normally a single item contains coordinates, datetime information, species names, observer names and related event or taxon information.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	We will connect our data to EOSC Matchmaker and pair data to be evaluated by the FAIR Assessment Toolkit.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	Most likely we will use some sized subsets of the all data as the data repository contains more than 50 million observations (50-100 GB). In addition to observation data, laji.fi has a lot of images, videos, bird sound recordings and taxonomic information.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Laji.fi data is coming from more than 500 sources including professional and amateur data sets. See more: https://laji.fi/en/theme/dataset-metadata
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Biodiversity researchers, public authorities, nature enthusiasts, private companies (consultants),
FAIR Data	

<p>1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>Data has already persistent identifiers. E.g. https://laji.fi/en/view?uri=http:%2F%2Ftun.fi%2FJX.2303461</p>
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>We already have metadata for all datasets (e.g. https://laji.fi/en/theme/dataset-metadata/HR.4511). It describes data sources, quality, collection methods, coverage, license and other additional information. However, we aim to improve our metadata as its quality varies and it is not fully machine readable yet.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Potentially</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Yes. Laji.fi has been certified as a Trustworthy Data Repository by CoreTrustSeal.</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Yes. Data is already deposited in laji.fi</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>

<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>95 % of the data is openly available. However, several reasons exist for why some content in biodiversity datasets should not be made public, but rather kept secret – either partially or completely – due to its sensitive nature. The most essential reasons are as follows:</p> <p>Nature conservation: endangered species, protection regulations, international environmental agreements and commitments, sensitivity to disturbances depending on time/location, etc.</p> <p>Data ownership and management: personal data, research use, business activities, etc.</p> <p>Biosafety: organisms harmful to humans, animals and plants, such as plant diseases, pests, etc.</p> <p>Read more: https://info.laji.fi/en/frontpage/sensitive-data/</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>It is usually 1 year for the sensitive data.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes. Users can download the data in standardized data formats (CSV, GeoPackage, Excel, TSV), use open APIs (JSON, GeoJSON) or view data in a browser (HTML).</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>For sensitive data, users may request it via a separate data request service or apply for an API key for a private data warehouse. For this project, we might have only a coarsened version of sensitive data in addition to open data.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>Users can log in to laji.fi or use API keys.</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>Yes but we will do it as we do every day.</p>

<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes. Metadata will contain a link where users can download the data as it is.</p> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>We don't have any plans to remove or archive data. All data will be public unless the data owner removes it (that rarely happens).</p> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Data can be used in any software that can handle tabular data (CSV, Excel), GIS formats (GeoPackage, GeoJSON), APIs or HTML data. We also aim to provide some example code snippets.</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>For data formats we will use GeoPackages, CSV, (Geo)JSON and Excel formats. Our APIs follow most recent standards (e.g. OGC API Features). Currently we are not fully using standardized vocabularies but we currently are aligning our data towards Darwin Core Vocabulary.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes we use unique identifiers.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>We are currently working on this. We have variable definitions in schema.laji.fi and in info.laji.fi but they are not complete. We also will provide readme files when users download data and we are planning to publish some code examples in GitHub.</p>

	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>Most of the data is published using open licenses. See: https://info.laji.fi/en/frontpage/datasets-and-their-use/ and https://info.laji.fi/en/frontpage/datasets-and-their-use/user-access-licenses/.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Hopefully.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Experts verify observations but they can't verify all of them manually. We are planning to implement automatic data quality checks that validates coordinates, timestamps, identifications and other information.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
<p>Other research outputs</p>	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>We don't have that kind of plans as far as I understand.</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	

<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Data in laji.fi will be maintained so far unless some data owners decide to remove it (that hasn't happened).</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>We have an user authentication system in place, sensitive data is secured and we take care of information security on a daily basis.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Ethical Aspects</p>	
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>	<p>We don't have much personal data. And if we do, we ask consents.</p>
<p>Other issues</p>	
<p>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</p>	

8.7. HADDOCK3 and DeepRank

WP/Task	WP7
Contact	Alexandre Bonvin (University of Utrecht)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In progress - this is the DMP for this project
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	No as users of the services are coming with their own data which are very project-specific
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	No re-use of existing data as users of the services are coming with their own data which are very project-specific. Their data can however come from established data bases like for example the Protein Data Bank (PDB). The computations (HADDOCK) do generate new data in the form of 3D models and various statistics.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	3D structures in PDB format (text files), various other input and output data (all as ASCII text files)
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Solving scientific problems involving the modelling of the biomolecular complexes.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	Input data: few MBs Output data: 100 MBs to a few GB
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Input data are provided by the user of the services Output data are the results of computations by the services
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	The data are very-much user-specific. Users have the ownership of the data. The services do not preserve the data (only kept for a limited period of time).

FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>It is the user responsibility to publish/share the data if relevant.</i>
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i> N.A.
	<i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i> N.A.
	<i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i> N.A.
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i> No - data is automatically deleted. It is the user's responsibility to store / share those.
	<i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i> N.A.
	<i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i> N.A.
b) Data:	<i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i> Users have the ownership of the data. It is their responsibility to share those if relevant.
	<i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i>

	N.A.
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>N.A. - Users have the ownership of the data. It is their responsibility to share those if relevant.</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
3.) Making data interoperable	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>The PDB format is a well established standard for sharing coordinates of 3D structures.</p>

D1.2 Data Management Plan

	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>We have online tutorials describing the use of the services and best practices guides.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>N.A.</p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
<p>Other research outputs</p>	

<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>The software behind the WeNMR services is open and freely available on GitHub under our own organisation (GitHub.com/haddocking):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ HADDOCK3: https://github.com/haddocking/haddock3 ■ DeepRank: https://github.com/haddocking/deeprank-gnn-esm ■ HADDOCK3-webapp (some of its components will be used to build the HADDOCK3 service): https://github.com/i-VRESSE/haddock3-webapp <p>The software of the webportal (wenmr.science.uu.nl) is also on GitHub, but as a private repository because of security issues (we don't want to expose the machinery behind the portal as we are constantly under attack):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● WeNMR portal software (private): https://github.com/haddocking/csbportal
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>The software is maintained on GitHub. Open source software is archived in the GitHub Arctic vault</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>N.A. as data are not stored (it is the responsibility of the user who remains the data owner)</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p>	<p>The software is stored and maintained on GitHub. Our open source software is archived in the GitHub Arctic vault</p>

Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA). N.A.
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	N.A.
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	Software-related projects have their own DMP. This is the case for example in the BioExcel Center of Excellence and national projects with the Netherlands eScience Center.

8.8. HAL

WP/Task	WP7
Contact	Nathalie Fargier - The National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<p><i>State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</i></p> <p>As part of the EOSC Data Commons project, we propose to use the metadata from HAL, France's national open repository for scholarly publications. These metadata are already publicly available via hal.science and API. We intend to connect these metadata to the Matchmaker.</p>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Yes, existing metadata will be re-used. The re-use will enable the enrichment of HAL metadata, thereby generating new metadata.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>EOSC Data Commons will re-use and generate metadata related to scholarly publications.</p> <p>Dublin Core, DCterms, BibTeX, DataCite, TEI, OpenAIRE, Codemeta (for software), RDF</p>
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	HAL metadata will be connected to the Matchmaker and associated with relevant datasets.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	https://hal.science/
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Researchers depositing their publications in HAL.

FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i>
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i>
	Both bibliographic metadata (title, author, publication details) and contextual metadata (abstract, keywords, affiliations and related resources) will be provided. Dublin Core, DCterms, BibTeX, DataCite, TEI, OpenAIRE, Codemeta (for software), RDF
	<i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i>
	Abstracts and keywords
	<i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i>
	Yes, metadata will be offered through API and OAI-PMH: API https://api.archives-ouvertes.fr/docs/search OAI-PMH https://api.archives-ouvertes.fr/oai/
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i>
	Yes, metadata will be deposited in HAL which is a trusted repository. HAL holds the CoreTrustSeal certification and is recognized by the European Research Council (ERC) as a compliant repository for long-term preservation and open access.
	<i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i>
	HAL is a partner of the project.
	<i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i>
	Yes

b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	c) Metadata:
<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>HAL ensures the long term preservation of its metadata through collaboration with a French data center (CINES -Centre Informatique National de l'Enseignement Supérieur)</p> <p>https://www.cines.fr/archivage/</p>	

	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>no</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Use of common standards for metadata : Dublin Core, DCterms, BibTeX, DataCite, TEI, OpenAIRE, Codemeta (for software), RDF</p> <hr/> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>n/a</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>HAL metadata can include qualified references to other data. We use the COAR Notify protocol to link HAL publications and their related datasets and software. We use DataCite for dataset citations and CodeMeta for software.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>n/a</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>n/a</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>n/a</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>

	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>n/a</p> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>The IT engineer to be hired.</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>The CCSD that operates HAL has an agreement with a data center (CINES) to ensure the long term preservation of metadata and scholarly publications. CINES is a French public institution under the supervision of the Ministry of Research and Higher Education. Its archiving platform complies with the OAIS (Open Archival Information System) reference model.</p> <p>https://about.hal.science/en/infrastructure/#long-term-preservation</p>
Data Security	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>HAL servers, along with metadata and publications, are hosted by the IN2P3 Computing Centre, a CNRS research and support unit. Additionally, a multi-site redundant backup system is implemented to ensure data safety, with one backup site already deployed at Inria.</p>

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, metadata will be stored in HAL, which is a trusted repository.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i> no
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	When depositing in HAL, researchers agree to the open dissemination of their publications and associated metadata by HAL.
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i> no

8.9. modama

WP/Task	7
Contact	Dieter Weber (FZJ)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	<p>Non</p> <p>The data generated by UC 9 modama in the context of EOSC Data Commons will be streamlined and integrated into the data and results for the other WPs. They will mostly consist of contributions to the development process such as requirements specifications and feedback; configurations for local deployments; and possibly code contributions.</p> <p>The data stored in and managed by modama at the ER-C, FZJ is not part of EOSC Data Commons. A separate DMP is in place at the ER-C for this data.</p> <p>In summary, a separate DMP for UC 9 modama in the context of EOSC Data Commons is not required.</p>
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	<i>State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</i>
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i>
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i>
	<i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i>
	<i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i>
	<i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i>
	<i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i>
b) Data:	<i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i>
	<i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i>
	<i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i>
	<i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i>

	<i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i>
	<i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i>
c) Metadata:	<i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i>
	<i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i>
	<i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i>
3.) Making data interoperable	<i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i>
	<i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i>
	<i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i>
4.) Increase data re-use	<i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i>
	<i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i>
	<i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i>
	<i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i>
	<i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i>

	<i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i>
Other research outputs	
In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?	<i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i>
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	<i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i>
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i>

D1.2 Data Management Plan

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i>

8.10. NFDI4Earth

WP/Task	7
Contact	Auriol Degbelo (TU Dresden)
Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.	In place In progress Non
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Yes, we reuse data from existing providers in the Earth System Sciences (ESS) in Germany and beyond (e.g. Helmholtz Earth and Environment DataHub, re3data, ...). The purpose of the reuse is twofold: increased visibility in a central portal for ESS resource search and recommendation of the best sources for researchers according to their needs.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	We are not generating new data
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	The project generates data in RDF (Resource Description Framework) format, as a unifying format for all types of resources provided (e.g. educational resources, publications, datasets, standards, repositories, etc)
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	N/A
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	Hundreds of Gigabytes
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The data comes from different providers in the Earth System Sciences, so the origin is manifold (e.g. re3data, Helmholtz Earth and Environment DataHub, ...)
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	The data is expected to be useful for researchers in the Earth System Sciences
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i> Yes

	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Yes. Metadata that are important here include those related to the spatial and temporal scope of a resource</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>No, the data is available through a SPARQL endpoint that we maintain</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Yes, the data is already openly available</p>

	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes, SPARQL</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>There are no restrictions</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Long-term availability is what we strive for. Since we maintain the data on our own infrastructure, we can guarantee availability until the end of the project funding (currently 2026 for the first project phase, tentatively 2031 for the second project phase)</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>The open-source code is available at https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/knowledgehub/kh-populator</p>

<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Since we have a broad variety of concepts, we reuse several vocabularies such as Schema.org and dcat. We also follow the best practices on spatial data provision on the Web (https://www.w3.org/TR/sdw-bp/) during publishing</p> <hr/> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Yes, we already do so. See, for example, the NFDI4Earth ontology (https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/)</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>We document the process for data creation from a technical perspective at https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/knowledgehub/kh-populator. The conceptual overview will be provided in a planned peer-reviewed publication</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>Yes, the data is available under the CC BY 4.0 licence</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes, it is useable by all interested parties</p>

	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Basic documentation of the provenance is planned, as we harvest data from some providers during the compilation of our knowledge graph. We will use the prov standard, where appropriate.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>We have validation of the conformance to our metadata schema, and also processes in place to identify dead links in the knowledge graph</p> <hr/> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>Other research outputs</p>	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Auriol Degbelo</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Discussion with various providers in the Earth System Sciences is ongoing regarding long-term preservation. Dumps of the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Graph will be regularly uploaded to Zenodo, so that snapshots remain persistently available.</p>
<p>Data Security</p>	

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	We use infrastructure from TUD Dresden, which takes care of security issues centrally. We do no work with sensitive data at the moment, as said above
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	N/A
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i> No
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	We do not deal with personal data at this point, hence this question is N/A
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i> NFDI4Earth is currently funded by the German Research Foundation, at least until September 2026. We have submitted a proposal for a follow-up funding, until 2031 and will get feedback about it in early 2026.

8.11. RRP

WP/Task	WP7, WP6, WP5
Contact	John Hennig (ETH Zurich)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	No.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	No.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	None.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Not applicable. (We are contributing code to the project, not research data.)
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	Not applicable.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Not applicable.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Not applicable.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i> Not applicable.

	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>

	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>

4.) Increase data re-use	<i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i>
	Not applicable.
	<i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i>
	Not applicable.
	<i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i>
	Not applicable.
	<i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i>
	Not applicable.
	<i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i>
	Not applicable.
	<i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i>
Other research outputs	
In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Yes. We are contributing software (RRP, Reproducible Research Platform) that is designed to help researchers follow FAIR principles.</p>
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	<p>Sebastian Luna Valero (WP7)</p> <p>Ales Krenek (WP6)</p> <p>Wim Hugo (WP5)</p>

How will long-term preservation be ensured?	We will make the code available on our public Gitlab instance, possibly on GitHub or GitLab.com as well, and we will archive software releases developed for the purpose of the EOSC Data Commons project on Zenodo and the ETH Data Archive for long-term preservation.
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	Long-term preservation as described above. The code will not include any sensitive data.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, code will be archived on Zenodo and in the ETH Data Archive for long-term preservation.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No.
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	Not applicable.
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial /departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	Possibly internal ones at ETH Zurich, if they apply.

8.12. ScienceMesh and CERNBox

WP/Task	WP7, WP6, WP5, WP4
Contact	Oliver Keeble (CERN), Giuseppe Lo Presti (CERN), Rasmus Oscar Welander (CERN)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Code from the CS3Mesh4EOSC project, OCM specification (https://github.com/cs3org/OCM-API), Reva codebase (https://github.com/cs3org/reva).
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Reusing code from the CS3Mesh4EOSC project (.go, .py) and building on this code, presentation templates (.pptx, .pdf)
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Code (.go, .py), presentations, and documents (.md, .pdf, .pptx)
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The purpose is to build on already semi-established standards such as the OCM (Open Cloud Mesh) protocol and integrate this with the EOSC eco-system, reusing presentation templates from EGI.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	~1-10gb
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Most of the code was written by developers at CERN.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Those wishing to integrate existing storage and data management systems into the services provided by the project.
FAIR Data	

1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i>
	No
	<i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i>
	Code will be hosted in public repositories and findable there.
	<i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i>
	No
	<i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i>
	Whatever is available in github
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i>
	Yes, https://github.com/cs3org/reva and https://github.com/EOSC-Data-Commons/Dispatcher
	<i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i>
	n/a
	<i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i>
	n/a
b) Data:	<i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i>
	n/a all code will be publicly available.
	<i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i>
	n/a

	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes (git)</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>No restrictions</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Code will be maintained in a public repository</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
3.) Making data interoperable	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>

	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
4.) Increase data re-use	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>n/a to code</p>
	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>Code is licensed Apache 2</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p> <p>n/a</p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Yes, the software and protocol are open source and managed.</p>
Allocation of resources	

Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	<i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i> Code will be published online
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	Backups, no sensitive data
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i> No
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	n/a
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i> Yes, CERN has their own data management procedures.

8.13. SWISSUbase

WP/Task	WP7
Contact	Stefanie Strebel (University of Zurich)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Existing data from SWISSUbase will be utilised based on the specific needs and requirements of the EOSC Data Commons project. Most importantly, the available (meta)data will be integrated with the EOSC Matchmaker.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	The reuse of existing data from SWISSUbase will not involve the generation of new data.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Data reuse will primarily focus on datasets from the social sciences and linguistics. Data will mostly be available in text or tabular formats, as well as audio, video, and image files. The specific file formats are predominantly open or widely recognised as standard within the respective disciplines.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	SWISSUbase (meta)data will be integrated with the EOSC Matchmaker to enhance discovery and reuse/analysis at the European level. Additionally, the data will be used for testing purposes.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The selection of data will be determined by the needs of the EOSC Data Commons project. Dataset sizes vary significantly depending on the types of data they contain. Technically, individual files can be as large as 950 GB, with no upper limit on the overall size of a dataset. As of July 2025, the SWISSUbase platform hosts nearly 1,250 published datasets.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	All data has been published on SWISSUbase.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Any researcher working with social sciences or linguistics data.
FAIR Data	

<p>1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i> DOIs have already been assigned to all datasets on SWISSUbase.</p>
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>In addition to a generic metadata schema, SWISSUbase has discipline-specific metadata schemas for the social sciences and linguistics, ensuring the availability of rich metadata as well as broad interoperability and alignment with international standards. For example, the metadata schema for linguistics, along with its controlled vocabularies, is based on META-SHARE and has been adapted to meet current requirements.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i> Yes, "keywords" is a mandatory metadata field for datasets published on SWISSUbase.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Metadata can be harvested via OAI-PMH. The metadata fields are currently mapped to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DataCite for technical metadata related to persistent identifiers • CMM 1.0/DDI Codebook 2.5 for the social sciences • MetaShare/CMDI for linguistics • Dublin Core DCMI as a general standard for cross-domain integration
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i> All data is available on SWISSUbase, which is a CoreTrustSeal-certified repository.</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i> The data has already been deposited, and since SWISSUbase is a use case partner in the EOSC Data Commons project, no arrangements are necessary.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i> All datasets deposited in SWISSUbase are assigned a DOI.</p>

<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Access to datasets on SWISSUbase is determined by the data depositors. Many datasets are published under closed access, requiring users to authenticate via a federated login and, in some cases, obtain prior approval from the data depositor. This restricted access reflects the nature of social science and linguistics datasets, which often include personal or sensitive information (e.g., interview transcripts, voice recordings). Openly available datasets are published under Creative Commons licenses.</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>An embargo option is available when publishing datasets on SWISSUbase, with the duration set by the data depositors.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Data on SWISSUbase is accessible through a free and standardised access protocol, but access depends on the level of restriction set by the data depositor. Users can download publicly available datasets without restrictions, while access to closed datasets requires a federated login (Switch edu-ID or CLARIN Federated Identity). Users can also retrieve specific datasets and files programmatically via an API.</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Compliance with the access conditions set by data depositors will be ensured throughout the EOSC Data Commons project.</p>

	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>No user identification is required for publicly accessible datasets. Access to closed datasets requires federated login via Switch edu-ID or CLARIN Federated Identity.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>For datasets requiring prior approval, access is granted directly by the data depositor.</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>All metadata on SWISSUbase is licensed under CC0. Data can be accessed via the download button in the dataset's metadata.</p> <hr/> <p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>All metadata remains available indefinitely. If a dataset is deleted, a tombstone page containing the metadata will be retained.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>If specific code or software is required, the data depositor will have provided relevant information in the documentation or metadata, or included the script directly with the dataset.</p>

<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Data curators ensure that all data available on SWISSUbase is published in an open format and/or in a format that is widely recognised as a standard in the respective disciplines. The metadata schemas adhere to discipline-specific standards, and a metadata user guide is available. Metadata is entered either through drop-down lists using controlled vocabularies or through free-text fields that follow specific input rules.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Within the project, the goal will more likely be to move towards a common standard rather than diverge from it, so this should not apply.</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Publications on SWISSUbase follow the structure: project → dataset(s) → file(s), where each project can contain multiple datasets that are grouped together. Therefore, related datasets are referenced through their overarching project.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>A team of data curators ensures that all datasets on SWISSUbase are published with rich metadata. They also verify whether additional documentation or README files have been provided to include any necessary information that cannot be entered directly into the platform. If such documentation is missing, the curators request the data depositor to add the required information or supplementary documents before the dataset is published.</p>

	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>The decision to make data openly accessible or restricted is left to the data depositor. When open publication is possible, the depositor can choose from any of the Creative Commons licenses.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>No new data is generated within the project; all data is already available on SWISSUbase and can be reused by third parties.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Data depositors include provenance information within the metadata/documentation associated with their datasets. Details about authors and participating institutions are collected in the project-level metadata.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>The metadata of every submitted dataset is thoroughly reviewed, and the data itself is spot-checked, by a team of data curators. Each project and its associated datasets are assigned two data curators. Any necessary corrections or additions are made in close consultation with the data depositor.</p> <hr/> <p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p>There are no plans in this regard.</p>
Allocation of resources	

Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	Presumably, each use case partner will handle this individually.
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	All data stored in SWISSUbase is retained for a minimum of 10 years, unless otherwise required by law.
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	All data is hosted on infrastructure operated by Switch. Physical access to the data centres (located in Zurich for production and Lausanne for backups) is restricted to authorised personnel. The storage platform uses Ceph S3 for both primary and backup storage. Network operations are managed by the Switch Cyber Security team. Access authentication relies on the Switch edu-ID and the CLARIN Federated Identity System, both of which require the use of secure passwords.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	Yes, SWISSUbase is CoreTrustSeal-certified.
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No. The data has already been published on SWISSUbase in compliance with applicable ethical and legal frameworks. For datasets with closed access, only the metadata will be made available through the EOSC Data Commons project.
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	Obtaining informed consent for data publication and long-term preservation is the responsibility of the data depositors. When submitting their datasets, they are prompted to confirm that this consent has been obtained.
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	This is not anticipated.

8.14. TopAnat

WP/Task	7
Contact	Tarcisio Mendes (SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In place
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Yes, the TopAnat tool is built upon the Bgee database (www.bgee.org). This tool was built and is maintained by the same organisation that owns the Bgee database, all data under public domain - CC0 licensed.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Yes, it generates new processed data for a specific task : anatomical entity enrichment analysis.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Data analysis output as text data (e.g., TSV, JSON).
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	TopAnat is a data analysis tool that takes some data (in a form of gene identifiers) as an input and maps genes to anatomical structures based on gene expression patterns from the Bgee database , the output data are these mappings with statistical information. Make this tool discoverable via the developed services in this project, and potentially, integrate the tool in a Virtual Research Environment such as Galaxy.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	Generated data: a few megabytes often kilobytes depending on the analysis done.
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	The TopAnat tool is built upon the Bgee database (www.bgee.org). This tool was built and maintained by the same organisation that owns the Bgee database, all data under public domain - CC0 licensed.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	Researchers interested in gene expression analysis.
FAIR Data	

1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p><i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i></p> <p>The TopAnat analysis is identified by a persistent identifier within the Bgee database (e.g., https://www.bgee.org/analysis/top-anat/8af5b0727ba1c62318707bf6f59c7c9c2b3697a1, https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/uberon). Moreover, the data the TopAnat uses to perform the analysis have persistent identifiers.</p>
	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>Metadata is provided including the use of a domain-specific controlled vocabulary the UBERON, ontology (e.g., https://www.bgee.org/analysis/top-anat/8af5b0727ba1c62318707bf6f59c7c9c2b3697a1, https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/uberon).</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes, it is the case. The data used by TopAnat is largely described using schema.org based metadata and domain specific ontologies.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes, the www.bgee.org website provides schema.org metadata (JSON-LD) in all gene pages, species pages (i.e., metadata about datasets per species) and main page that can be harvested.</p>
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>TopAnat analysis is already part of a domain specific trusted repository. Indeed, Bgee is recognised as a global core biodata resource (https://globalbiodata.org/what-we-do/global-core-biodata-resources/list-of-current-global-core-biodata-resources/).</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p>

b) Data:	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>All data is openly available under a public domain dedication CC0.</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>All metadata is openly available under a public domain dedication CC0.</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Bgee is committed to long term preservation of its data and tools. We have been keeping archive versions of the data, website services and tools since 2009. For example, this TopAnat analysis relies on the Bgee database 13.2 released in 2016, the same analysis can be executed using the latest data and tool version in 2025, https://archives.bgee.org/13-2/?page=top_anat#/result/7919f27d1</p>

	<p>43667bc6c137401ce0c91b51e257538/ . This assures that TopAnat analysis is fully reproducible over time.</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>It is all open source (https://github.com/BgeeDB) and documented (https://www.bgee.org/support/tutorials).</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Bgee is recognised as an ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability resource (https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/interoperability/rirs). It re-uses several domain specific ontologies and general-purpose vocabularies such as schema.org.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p> <p><i>Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>TopAnat results include links to controlled vocabularies used to annotate the Bgee data. Moreover, the Bgee database provides cross-references to several other life science databases such as uniprot.org.</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Readme files, tutorial and documentations as markdown and rendered in the Bgee website (see https://www.bgee.org/support/tutorials).</p> <p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>All data is CC0 and the code is open-source and freely available to reuse.</p>

	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Not applicable for the TopAnat tools. It only uses data from the Bgee database.</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	<p>Frederic Bastian</p>
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p>
Data Security	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>	<p>All data security aspects for this use case are managed by the Bgee database.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for</p>	<p>Yes, it is managed and curated by the Bgee team.</p>

<p>long-term preservation and curation?</p>	
<p>Ethical Aspects</p>	
<p>Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p>	<p>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</p>
<p>Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>	<p>No.</p>
<p>Other issues</p>	
<p>Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial /departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?</p>	<p>Please list and briefly describe them.</p>

8.15. VIP

WP/Task	WP7 UC 15
Contact	Sorina Pop (CNRS)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In progress
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	We will re-use data acquired on the PILoT imaging platform at CREATIS
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Yes, data processing will generate new data
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>Data come mainly in two formats: (i) DICOM standard (including raw data and metadata) and (ii) a Bruker (constructor) proprietary format, containing a text (metadata) and a binary file.</p> <p>The processing of the data will involve the following format transformation: Bruker format to mrui file format and LCModel file (.RAW) format for the MR spectroscopy data, Dicom to MRTRix3 file format (.mih) Quantification results of spectroscopy data are stored in text and json file formats.</p>
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<p>Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) is a medical imaging technique that exploits the magnetic properties of biological tissues to determine their chemical composition. In particular, we can use the magnetic resonance signal to estimate in vivo the concentration of certain metabolites (e.g.: neurotransmitters, amino acids) at a certain location in the body (e.g.: a region of the brain). This requires specific acquisition protocols and reconstruction and quantification pipelines that need to be studied to increase the robustness, reproducibility and reliability of measurements.</p> <p>This use case covers the whole MRS data lifecycle, from acquisition to storage, management, analysis and reuse. Data is acquired on the PILoT facility and stored in a Girder warehouse with associated metadata. Data is then processed with tools available on VIP and results are pushed back to the Girder warehouse.</p>
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	We expect to use and generate data of approximately 50 GB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Data is stored on the Girder warehouse at CREATIS
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	To MRS researchers.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	This is work in progress, but we envisage to associate a DOI to data collections stored on Girder.
	Metadata are extracted from the DICOM headers, but are also collected at acquisition time based on information provided by the operator. They are stored both in text files and associated with data through the Girder metadata mechanism as described in the README available in the Girder collection.
	Yes, we plan to provide search keywords in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use
	<i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i> Under investigation
2.) Making data openly accessible	
a) Repository:	Data will remain on the Girder warehouse at CREATIS
	This is work in progress, but we envisage to associate a DOI to data collections stored on Girder.
b) Data:	<i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i> Data access is currently restricted. They will be distributed under a CC-BY license after the publication of the related research work currently ongoing

	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p>
	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p>
c) Metadata:	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p>
3.) Making data interoperable	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p>
	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p>
	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p>
4.) Increase data re-use	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p>

	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <p>Data quality is assessed at processing time, using the usual metrics and assessments such as SNR and linewidth for spectra.</p>
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>
Other research outputs	
<p>In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?</p>	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p>
Allocation of resources	
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?</p>	
<p>How will long-term preservation be ensured?</p>	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p>
Data Security	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and</p>	

transfer of sensitive data)?	
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>For this use-case, there is no personal data (subjects are rats).</p> <p>Ethical issues and code of conduct w.r.t. acquisition protocols on animals are handled by the PILoT imaging platform.</p> <p>The project relies on two authorizations APAFIS#25081-2020050712321671 v1 and APAFIS#30495-2018121414354904 v6 respectively for the use of an animal model of multiple sclerosis and healthy rats, and respectively delivered the 11th of May 2020 and the 25th of March 2021 by the French ministry of education, research and innovation to collect data from small animal in vivo imaging</p>
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	<p>For this use-case, there is no personal data (subjects are rats).</p>
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<p><i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i></p>

8.16. DANS - KNAW

WP/Task	7
Contact	Wim Hugo (DANS-KNAW)
<i>Established a DMP, addressing important aspects of RDM.</i>	In place In progress Non
Data Summary	
Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?	Yes- data harvested from participating repositories, and from tool inventories such as Galaxy and WorkflowHub.
Will you re-use any existing data and will this generate new data?	Data will be harmonised and extended to create new datasets.
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	Inputs data mostly in JSON or XML formats, new datasets will be JSON or JSON-LD.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Establish the Catalogue of Tools - these datasets are inventories used by the application.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	< 1GB
What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	Obtained from managed or curated sources, manually quality assured and curated prior to publication.
To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	All researchers and developers of research data infrastructure.
FAIR Data	
1.) Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<i>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</i> Yes, by periodically publishing snapshots in Zenodo.

	<p><i>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</i></p> <p>No, limited to Zenodo metadata, which should be adequate.</p>
	<p><i>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</i></p> <p>Yes.</p>
	<p><i>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</i></p> <p>Yes, via Zenodo.</p>
<p>2.) Making data openly accessible</p>	
<p>a) Repository:</p>	<p><i>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</i></p> <p>No</p>
	<p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</i></p> <p>No need, Zenodo is publicly available for such outputs.</p>
	<p><i>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</i></p> <p>Assigned by Zenodo.</p>
<p>b) Data:</p>	<p><i>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p>Yes, CC4 BY licence.</p>
	<p><i>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>Not applicable.</p>

	<p><i>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?</i></p> <p>Yes - OAI-PMH.</p>
	<p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Operational data is subject to AAI and privileges for updates and additions.</p>
	<p><i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i></p> <p>EOSC or EGI SSO</p>
	<p><i>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</i></p> <p>No</p>
<p>c) Metadata:</p>	<p><i>Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</i></p> <p>Snapshots are available indefinitely (linked to Zenodo sustainability)</p>
	<p><i>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read or process the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</i></p> <p>Yes, narrative description published with snapshot(s).</p>
<p>3.) Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</i></p> <p>Metadata is based on IANA MIME types and Codemeta</p>

	<p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?</i></p>
	<p><i>Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>4.) Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</i></p> <p>Methodology description accompanies snapshot.</p>
	<p><i>Will your data be made openly available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Under which license?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
	<p><i>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</i></p> <p>Yes, RO-Crate for snapshot provenance.</p>
	<p><i>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Harmonisation and standardisation of data type references/ vocabulary, based on MIME Types - human curation. 2. Harmonisation of tool descriptions using (extended) Codemeta schema - human curation 3. Harmonisation of platform descriptions based on TOSCA templates developed by EOSC Beyond.
	<p><i>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security, and ethical aspects.</i></p>

	Code will be archived in Software Heritage and described using CodeMeta
Other research outputs	
In addition to the management of data, are you also considering and planning for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the projects?	<p><i>Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) Are those also following FAIR principles?</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Code will be archived in Software Heritage and described using CodeMeta Landscape review and specifications are published openly as a project deliverable
Allocation of resources	
Who will be responsible for data management in your WP/Task?	
How will long-term preservation be ensured?	<p><i>(costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)</i></p> <p>Published in free-to-use repositories (Zenodo, Software Heritage, EU facilities).</p>
Data Security	
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p>Dependent on provisions by Zenodo, Software Heritage, EU facilities, which are assumed to be adequate.</p> <p>Code is also available in GitHub</p> <p>Data snapshots can be stored redundantly on EGI infrastructure.</p>
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?	
Ethical Aspects	
Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<p><i>Yes or No. (If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action DoA).</i></p> <p>No</p>
Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in	Not applicable

D1.2 Data Management Plan

questionnaires dealing with personal data?	
Other issues	
Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/depart mental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?	<i>Please list and briefly describe them.</i> No.

9. Conclusions and next steps

The EOSC Data Commons's DMP is a complete data management approach that complies with Horizon Europe recommendations and that aims to make data as findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR) as feasible.

The DMP relies on technological solutions like OpenAIRE initiative, GitHub, EGI Document Repository, Zenodo, and Google Drive for the execution of these processes. Additionally, this will ensure that the data created or compiled throughout the EOSC Data Commons project, including open data and public publications, will be kept and continue to be usable once the project is completed.

The DMP is intended to safeguard the analysis of compiled/created data based on the level of their privacy and to use an alternate sharing methodology relying upon this level. Confidential information or information that raises ethical problems will not be released.

Finally, the DMP is built on guaranteeing appropriately informed consent, and protecting each participant's zone of privacy, while adhering to GDPR guidelines.

9.1. DMP Change Management

This DMP is considered a living document, and it will be updated during the project to reflect the most recent developments and conclusions. In actuality, the early version of the DMP will be expanded and enhanced at least once more on M18 of the project. Ad hoc improvements may also be deployed if deemed necessary. In general, changes need to be fully compliant with EU laws and best practices in research data management.

Updates will be entered in the changelog table that is shown on the confluence page of the concerned DMP. Analogously, the distribution of notifications on updates will be realised via the regular meetings (WPs, WP leaders, PMO, AMB).

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GDPR	EU General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
RI	Research Infrastructure
WP	Work Package

Acronyms: <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/EGIG>